

Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for Dataset Elements in Qualiservice

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Abstract

This report presents the results of the completed feasibility study on assigning Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) to individual elements of qualitative datasets at Qualiservice, the data service center for qualitative social research. The project was conducted within the framework of KonsortSWD Measure 5.1 - Enhancing PID services as a base for a FAIR data infrastructure. The study aimed to evaluate and implement a scalable workflow for PID registration on the dataset element level, including text excerpts, audio/video segments, and image area. The project successfully mapped the Qualiservice metadata structure to the KonsortSWD PID Registration Service, extending metadata for various qualitative data types. The pilot implementation demonstrated the viability of manual and semi-automated registration using JSON file metadata, with persistent identifiers resolving the specific metadata sections corresponding to each dataset element. Challenges related to access behind login barriers and ambiguities were addressed through practical solutions, such as fragment identifiers and W3C-compliant landing page structures. The study concludes that assigning PIDs at the element level in qualitative research is feasible and beneficial since it enhances data citation, findability, and long-term reusability.

Keywords

Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), Granular Data Citation, Research Data Infrastructure, Social Sciences - Qualitative Data, Dataset Elements.

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1. Motivation

Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) are increasingly essential in research data management, ensuring digital objects are uniquely referenceable and persistently accessible. PIDs are often assigned to research outputs such as papers and datasets. Due to its growing recognition for enabling traceability and machine-actionable features, other instances, such as institutions¹, projects, and funding programs², authors³, and instruments⁴ have been assigned a PID. Quantitative data, such as tables and statistical data packages, are also identified by a PID. However, due to its increasingly large size in terms of content (for instance, the number of variables), a single PID cannot unambiguously identify these dataset elements, such as variables or questions within a survey dataset. The challenge is even more complex for qualitative data, where datasets (or collections of data) often contain heterogeneous elements like audio or text files, video segments, and image areas for a specific number of individual cases. To address these challenges, we rely on assigning a PID on a more fine-grained level, providing unique identification and long-term accessibility on a lower granularity level, on the level of a dataset element.

Qualiservice⁵ at the University of Bremen is a research data center that archives and provides qualitative research data from the various fields of the social sciences for scientific re-use. To date, Qualiservice is the only RDC in Germany that curates all types of qualitative data (interviews, observations, and ethnographic data as text, audio, and video) independent of topic and discipline. It archives curated datasets for secondary reuse and offers their metadata adhering to the FAIR principles via DataCite and the DDI 3.2 metadata standard. However, the current infrastructure⁶ only allows citation and PID assignment at the dataset level⁷, not at the granular level of individual elements of the datasets themselves.

To improve citation accuracy and support reusability, this short project investigates how PIDs can be feasibly assigned to dataset elements within qualitative data (e.g., individual files like text documents, audio, video, or image files, interview excerpts, video and sound segments, image areas) and how the metadata infrastructure must evolve to support this approach. Our motivation for proposing and executing the PID Feasibility Study for Qualiservice as a short project during 2025 was to investigate how persistent identification of qualitative dataset types can be technically and conceptually enabled to improve citation practices and the FAIRness of data and metadata.

¹ <https://ror.org/>

² <https://raid.org>

³ <https://orcid.org/>

⁴ <https://docs.pidinst.org/en/latest/>

⁵ <https://www.qualiservice.org/en/>

⁶ Qualiservice is operated by several partners in a consortium and is located at the University of Bremen at the Research Center on Inequality and Social Policy (SOCIUM). The technical and infrastructural development of Qualiservice is carried out in cooperation with PANGAEA® - Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science doi:10.1594/PANGAEA

⁷ https://wiki.pangaea.de/wiki/Qualiservice_Search,_Interoperability_and_Services#Datasets

The goal is to extend PID assignment beyond the dataset level to individual elements within qualitative datasets, thereby promoting findability and posterior reusability through finer granular identification, disambiguation, and following data referencing.

This short project was conducted in the context of KonsortSWD-NFDI4society⁸, a consortium of the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI)⁹. NFDI focuses on advancing science and research by establishing a comprehensive research data infrastructure on a national level. KonsortSWD aims to strengthen the research data infrastructure for the social, behavioral, educational, and economic sciences. KonsortSWD provides tailored services to researchers and research data centers, emphasizing data-sharing practices that align with the FAIR principles. It seeks to enhance data availability and provide comprehensive support throughout the research lifecycle, particularly in managing data effectively. In the context of NFDI, this project is classified as follows:

- **Objective:**
Enable the assignment, storage, and display of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for dataset elements in Qualiservice (e.g., individual files like text documents, audio, video, or image files, interview excerpts, sound segments, image areas) by aligning the existing metadata infrastructure with the PID registration schema developed in KonsortSWD-NFDI4society Measure 5.1.
- **Approach:**
Map Qualiservice's current metadata system¹⁰, which is operated by Data Publisher PANGAEA, and aligned with the DDI 3.2. Specification and the Qualitative Data Model for DDI [1], to the PID schema; create prototype JSON metadata files for individual dataset elements; evaluate the feasibility of assigning unique landing pages to elements sharing the same dataset URL; and identify workflow adjustments required for full implementation.
- **Final Product:**
A feasibility report containing a model for PID registration and a set of recommendations for metadata required for persistent and fine-grained identification of qualitative dataset elements.

⁸ <https://www.konsortswd.de/ueber-uns/konsortswd/>

⁹ <https://www.nfdi.de>

¹⁰ https://wiki.pangaea.de/wiki/Qualiservice_Data_Model

- **Target Group:**
Research data centers that store and provide qualitative data, such as Qualiservice and KonsortSWD-associated infrastructures, seek to implement persistent identifiers for element-level data citation.
- **Benefits for NFDI:**
Increased findability and interoperability of qualitative data through persistent, machine-actionable metadata; support for integration with EOSC and other consortia; contribution to the NFDI Metadata Section's efforts to standardize and link heterogeneous data sources at a granular level.

This report is an outcome of Measure TA.5-M.1 of KonsortSWD-NFDI4society (short 5.1: PID Registration Service), addressing Milestone 6: Support of the Implementation of registration by Use Case Partner. The primary objective of Measure 5.1 is to assign PID on a finer-grained level, such as about quantitative data, survey variables, and questions [2]. In addition to the service, qualitative data fragments, such as audio and video segments and image areas, were implemented. KonsortSWD's PID service adds significant value by providing a stable and permanent way to reference and cite data at a granular level. This enhances academic recognition and the validation of research outputs, ensuring that data is findable and accessible in the long term [3]. PIDs are a key element of the FAIR Principles [4]. This measure is particularly relevant because public PID providers, like DataCite[5] do not support PID assignment below the dataset level. KonsortSWD's PID service thus addresses this critical gap.

Milestone 6 outlines the efforts and strategic implementations undertaken in 2024 and 2025 to map metadata with the PID registration service schema [6] and to assign test PIDs within KonsortSWD's data centers. Reports presenting other use case implementations are the German Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP), located at the German Institute for Economic Research (DIW) (implemented in 2023) [7] and the Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies (DZHW) (implemented in 2024) [8].

This project reports on a feasibility study to ensure persistent identification with the current structure of qualitative data held by Qualiservice. To this end, the data model of the Qualiservice system has been mapped to match the PID registration metadata schema for conceptualizing a test phase. We relied on some dataset examples (See section 3.1), creating JSON files with the required metadata for manual dataset elements registration and test PIDs assignment. To achieve these goals, this report is structured as follows:

Section 2 presents the metadata schema and extensions used in the project. It begins by detailing the core metadata fields adopted from the KonsortSWD Measure 5.1 schema and their alignment with the DataCite 4.4 standard. It then introduces the fields required to describe fragments, such as time offsets or character positions, depending on the media type (text, audiovisual, sound, or image). An additional subsection describes extended fields that support integration into knowledge graphs and linked data environments.

Section 3 outlines the types of digital objects considered for PID registration – including complete resources and elements such as audio segments or text excerpts – and examines the current state of the Qualiservice metadata infrastructure. It discusses the limitations of existing dataset-level metadata and the need for more granular and interoperable metadata schemas to support element-level PID assignment.

Section 4 provides recommendations for PID service implementation, balancing technical feasibility and conceptual soundness. Topics include managing the trade-off between metadata granularity and practicality, promoting interoperability across systems, integrating persistent identifiers into citation workflows, and enhancing compatibility with knowledge graphs through iterative testing.

Section 5 compiles supporting figures and tables, while Section 6 (Appendix) provides sample metadata and test PIDs for all major entity types: audiovisual, image, sound, and text, including both complete resources and their respective fragments. Supplementary data, such as JSON files for all registered and PID-generated elements, are available.

2. The Metadata Schema and Extensions

This section presents the metadata schema and extensions used in the short project. It details the (2.1) core metadata fields adopted from the KonsortSWD Measure 5.1 schema. It then introduces the (2.2) specific fields required to describe fragments, such as time offsets or character positions, depending on the media type (text, audiovisual, sound, or image). An additional subsection describes extended fields to support integration into (2.3) knowledge graphs and linked data environments.

To support PID registration for a diverse range of qualitative dataset elements, the project adopts and extends the metadata schema defined by KonsortSWD Measure 5.1 [9]. These fields align with DataCite standards and are designed to be machine-actionable and interoperable across PID systems.

2.1 Core Metadata Fields

Table 1 presents the metadata fields selected for this purpose, detailing their function, obligation level, and interoperability alignment with DataCite specifications.

ID	Field Name	Description	Requirement in the PID Service	DataCite Obligation
1	Study DOI	DOI or PID of the parent dataset. Transferred from the parent resource.	Required	Mandatory (M)
2	Entity Name	Name/ID of the element (e.g., variable, audio segment).	Required	Optional (O)
3	Entity Label	Readable label/title of the element.	Required	Optional (O)
4	PID Proposal	Custom string for PID registration. In this case, the Test PID prefix is used.	Required	Optional (O)
5	Landing Page	The (URL) landing page of the element to register, with a detailed description of the element.	Required	Optional (O)
6	Resource Type	Controlled vocabulary describing the element type (e.g., image, sound).	Required	Mandatory (M)
7	Title	Auto-generated title combining Entity Name and Entity Label.	Required	Mandatory (M)
8	Creators	People or institutions responsible for the resource. Transferred from the parent resource.	Required	Mandatory (M)
9	Publisher	The entity responsible for distributing the resource. Transferred from the parent resource.	Required	Mandatory (M)
10	Publication Date	YYYY-MM-DD format publication date. Transferred from the parent resource.	Required	Mandatory (M)
11	Availability	Access conditions (e.g., OnSite, Delivery). Transferred from the parent resource.	Required	—

ID	Field Name	Description	Requirement in the PID Service	DataCite Obligation
12	Description	Additional metadata, abstract, or commentary. Transferred from the parent resource.	Optional	Recommended (R)

Table 1: PID Registration Service: Core Metadata Fields

The PID Registration Service employs a standardized metadata schema defined by KonsortSWD Measure 5.1 to support interoperability. Table 1 overviews the metadata schema required to register each dataset element. It ensures compatibility and machine-actionability across PID infrastructures. This structured approach is critical given the nature of Qualiservice's collections, which include diverse qualitative formats and smaller components. The following section explains how the metadata schema is applied to describe the qualitative data fragments from Qualiservice metadata required to describe qualitative data elements

Qualiservice data collections include various qualitative data formats and types: interviews, field notes, audio, video, and images, often fragmented into specific sub-elements. These elements – such as audio segments or text excerpts – can be considered discrete digital objects for PID registration. When a dataset includes text content, segments or excerpts (fragments) from a larger resource, such as a text file, can be registered and assigned a PID. Hence, specific metadata fields are required to define their boundaries and maintain context. This section outlines how each entity type represents complete resources and fragments.

Resource Type	Granularity	Metadata container in JSON format	Example
Audiovisual	Full: Metadata for a complete audiovisual item seeks to register the entire file (e.g., complete video)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "entityType": "Audiovisual" • "isFragment": false • Standard metadata (See 2.1 Core Metadata Fields). 	<pre>{ "entityType": "Audiovisual", "isFragment": false, "startOffset": "n/a", "endOffset": "n/a" }</pre>
	Fragments: (e.g., video clips)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "entityType": "Audiovisual" • "isFragment": true • Standard metadata (See 2.1 Core Metadata Fields). • "startOffset" and "endOffset" in HH:MM:SS format to indicate the exact timing of the clip within the complete resource. 	<pre>{ "entityType": "Audiovisual", "isFragment": true, "startOffset": "00:03:15", "endOffset": "00:04:02" }</pre>

Resource Type	Granularity	Metadata container in JSON format	Example
Images	Full: Metadata for a complete Image item seeks to register the entire file (e.g., complete Image)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "entityType": "Image" • "isFragment": false • Standard metadata (See 2.1 Core Metadata Fields). 	<pre>{ "entityType": "Image", "isFragment": false, "Shape": {n/a "Coordinates": { n/a } }</pre>
	Fragments: (e.g., cropped region)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "entityType": "Image" • "isFragment": true • "Shape": Rec. • "Coordinates": wywh • "x", "y", "width", "height" for the region of interest. • Standard metadata (See 2.1 Core Metadata Fields). 	<pre>{ "entityType": "Image", "isFragment": true, "Shape": { "Coordinates": { "x": 100, "y": 50, "width": 200, "height": 150 } } }</pre>
Sound	Full: Metadata for a complete Sound item seeks to register the entire file (e.g., complete sound file)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "entityType": "Sound" • "isFragment": false • Standard metadata (See 2.1 Core Metadata Fields). 	<pre>{ "entityType": "Sound", "isFragment": false, "startOffset": "n/a", "endOffset": "n/a" }</pre>
	Fragments: (e.g., sound segments)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "entityType": "Sound" • "isFragment": true • "startOffset" and "endOffset" in HH:MM:SS to mark clip duration • Standard metadata (See 2.1 Core Metadata Fields). 	<pre>{ "entityType": "Sound", "isFragment": true, "startOffset": "00:00:10", "endOffset": "00:01:20" }</pre>

Resource Type	Granularity	Metadata container in JSON format	Example
Text	Full: Metadata for a complete Text item seeks to register the entire file (e.g., complete text file)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "entityType": "Text" • "isFragment": false • Standard metadata (See 2.1 Core Metadata Fields). 	<pre>{ "entityType": "false", "isFragment": true, "startCharOffset": "n/a", "endCharOffset": "n/a" }</pre>
	Fragments: (e.g., Text excerpts or annotated phrases)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "entityType": "Text" • "isFragment": true • "startCharOffset" and "endCharOffset" to define the range of characters • Standard metadata (See 2.1 Core Metadata Fields). 	<pre>{ "entityType": "Text", "isFragment": true, "startCharOffset": "13", "endCharOffset": "99" }</pre>

Table 2: PID Registration Service: metadata fields for qualitative dataset elements

This structure ensures that each fragment is clearly linked to its parent resource (resourcePID) and uniquely identifiable via a pidProposal, supporting precise citation, reuse, and digital preservation. Also, these annotations support accurate referencing and interoperability across platforms.

2.2 Knowledge graphs and linked data environments

Some value types from the Core metadata embedded machine-actionable features, for instance: Study DOI, the PID Proposal, the Landing Page, and the Resource type are metadata fields whose values are either PIDs, URLs, or controlled vocabulary terms. For this reason, these values can be applied to build a knowledge graph visualization. However, a relationship container field was adopted for addressing other relations among entities, including the following fields:

ID	Field Name	Description	Requirement in the PID Service	Controlled Vocabulary
13	RelatedItem	Related object (e.g., a dataset linked to an entity)	Optional	Resource Type values
13.1	RelatedIdentifier	PID of the related object	Mandatory if RelatedItem is used.	PID syntax
13.1.1	RelatedIdentifier_Type	Type of PID system (e.g., DOI, Handle) of the related object	Mandatory if RelatedIdentifier is used.	PID schemes (DOI, Handles, ORCID, etc.)
13.1.2	Relation_Type	Nature of the relationship (e.g., IsPartOf, Describes)	Mandatory if RelatedItem is used.	DataCite terms, Variables relations CV [10].

Table 3: Metadata container for relation fields for registering a dataset element.

Section 3 outlines the types of digital objects considered for PID registration – including complete resources and fragmented elements such as audio segments or text excerpts – and examines the current state of the Qualiservice metadata infrastructure. It discusses the limitations of existing dataset-level metadata and the need for more granular and interoperable metadata schemas to support element-level PID assignment.

3. The digital objects and the existing infrastructure

Currently, the Qualiservice metadata schema¹¹ provides URLs only at the dataset level (a PID for a collection of data objects)¹². However, assigning PIDs at the element level requires additional metadata granularity. As Qualiservice uses PANGAEA's technical infrastructure and data model¹³, the additional required information is already available in tabular form. This table contains "micrometadata"¹⁴ or metadata about the individual data objects/elements that make up a dataset, organised in *data series* grouped by *parameters*¹⁵. Each metadata record for a digital object, or part of it, is therefore represented as a row in the table. It would optimally require unique landing pages for each element to improve disambiguation and addressability, rather than pointing to data rows in an HTML table. The metadata schema used in the PID registration service [11] was updated with required specific extensions to support qualitative elements, datatypes, and full interoperability [12].

The goals are:

- Mapping the data model of the Qualiservice system to match the PID registration metadata schema for conceptualizing a test phase;
- Create JSON files with the required metadata for manual PID registration;
- Assign Test PID registration through manual JSON files, and;
- Propose infrastructure adjustments for sustainable integration.

To bridge the gap between the metadata granularity required for element-level PID registration and the technical capabilities needed to operationalize this process, the updated PID registration metadata schema was aligned with Qualiservice's data model. This alignment laid the groundwork for using the existing metadata schema and converting it into the required JSON format. With this conceptual mapping, the next step involved testing the registration at the KonsortSWD PID Registration Service. This process used the steps to register test PIDs for qualitative data elements manually.

3.1 Existing Infrastructure

The KonsortSWD PID Registration Service is a prototype tool developed within the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) to assign persistent identifiers (PIDs) to dataset elements below the study or dataset level, such as individual survey variables or qualitative data files. Users access the PID Registration Service through a web-based platform. After receiving their

¹¹ https://wiki.pangaea.de/wiki/Qualiservice_Data_Model

¹² https://wiki.pangaea.de/wiki/Qualiservice_Search,_Interoperability_and_Services#Datasets

¹³ https://wiki.pangaea.de/wiki/Data_model

¹⁴ https://wiki.pangaea.de/wiki/Qualiservice_Search,_Interoperability_and_Services

¹⁵ https://wiki.pangaea.de/wiki/Data_series and https://wiki.pangaea.de/wiki/Qualiservice_Parameters

login credentials, they can enter the system to register dataset elements and monitor the status of PID assignments. The following image shows the homepage of the service interface.

Figure 1: Homepage of the KonsortSWD PID Registration Service.

The service allows users to test PID assignment, monitor registration status (e.g., pending, finished, failed), and access metadata through structured identifiers. It relies on the ePIC API and the Handle system. Once logged in, users are directed to the Status Page of the KonsortSWD PID Registration Service. This interface provides an overview of PID registration activity linked to the user account. Figure 2 shows the status dashboard for the user **qservice** [13], summarizing 21 submitted registration jobs. Of these, 16 have been successfully completed (Finished), 4 are currently in progress (Pending/Running), and 1 has failed (Failed). This status view allows users to monitor the progress of their PID assignments.

Figure 2: User-Specific PID Registration Status Dashboard showing job progress and outcomes for the user **qservice.**

To register a variable or other dataset element with a Persistent Identifier (PID) using the KonsortSWD PID Registration Service, the data provider first prepares the necessary metadata, including the fragment identifier, the parent dataset's DOI, and the element type (e.g., variable, audio segment, transcript). This metadata is then submitted via the ePIC API in a structured JSON format that complies with the KonsortSWD PID schema. Once submitted, the system assigns a test PID to the element and updates its registration status (e.g., pending, finished, or failed). Registered PIDs can be resolved to specific metadata fragments within the dataset's landing page,

Figure 3 shows the Swagger interface for the KonsortSWD PID Registration Service API. This interface provides a user-friendly way to interact with the backend services to verify and register PIDs using HTTP requests. Each function is documented and can be tested directly in the interface (after authorization).

Key Steps Displayed:

1. POST /entity/verify
This step checks whether the metadata (submitted in a JSON file) is valid. It returns a validation report without registering the data yet. (See Figure 4).
2. POST /entity/register
After successful verification, this endpoint is used to register the metadata and PID. A jobid is generated to track the status of this operation. (See Figure 7).
3. GET /entity/status/jobs/{username}
Retrieves a list of all PID registration jobs submitted by a specific user. (See Figure 2).

4. GET /entity/status/job/{jobId}
Checks the detailed status of a specific registration or verification job using its jobId. (See Figure 8).

Figure 3: Swagger interface of the KonsortSWD PID Registration Service showing the available API endpoints for verification, registration, and job monitoring.

Figure 4 details the first step of the PID registration process using the Swagger API interface: metadata verification. The user begins by selecting an appropriate entityType, in this case, AUDIOVISUAL, from a predefined list of data categories. This ensures the correct metadata schema is applied during validation. Then, a sample JSON file containing the metadata to be tested is selected—in this example, audiovisual_valid.json.

Once submitted, the system checks the structure and content of the metadata file against the expected format and provides a validation report. This step is essential to detect errors or inconsistencies before attempting PID registration.

Figure 4: Swagger Interface – Step 1: Metadata Verification

Figure 5 displays a completed example of the /entity/verify request for an audiovisual entity. The user uploads a valid metadata file for an audiovisual fragment. After selecting the file audiovisual_valid.json, the JSON content is displayed in the Swagger interface. The file includes resourcePID, entityType, isFragment, landingPage, and creators. This file also includes metadata about a specific video fragment—such as its timecodes (startOffset, endOffset), title, label, and associated persistent identifier (pidProposal). The system parses and validates the file before PID registration. The metadata also links to the dataset's landing page, allowing future users to interpret the fragment within its broader research context.

Figure 5: Swagger Interface – Audiovisual Metadata Validation Example

Figure 6 shows the server response after successfully validating the JSON metadata via the /entity/verify endpoint. The response code 200 indicates that the verification was successful and that all PID entities were validated correctly.

The response body includes:

- documentUri: A URI pointing to the validated document (10.4232/1.1680 in this example).
- constraintViolation: An empty array [], confirming that no schema violations were detected.

Below the response body, the response headers confirm that the interaction occurred over a secure connection and returned JSON-formatted data. This step concludes the verification phase, allowing the user to proceed with registration.

Server response

Code	Details
200	<p>Response body</p> <pre>{ "documentId": "10.4232/1.1640", "constraintViolation": [] }</pre> <p>Response headers</p> <pre>cache-control: no-cache,no-store,max-age=0,must-revalidate connection: keep-alive content-length: 57 content-type: application/json date: Thu, 07 Aug 2025 22:58:24 GMT expires: 0 keep-alive: timeout=60 pragma: no-cache vary: Origin,Access-Control-Request-Method,Access-Control-Request-Headers x-content-type-options: nosniff x-frame-options: SAMEORIGIN x-xsd-protection: 0</pre>

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	All PID entities verified correctly	No links

Media type:

Controls Accept header:

Example Value | Schema

```
{
  "documentId": "string",
  "constraintViolations": [
    {
      "message": "string",
      "locationInfo": "string"
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 6: Swagger Interface – Successful Metadata Verification Response

After successfully validating the PID metadata in the previous step using the /entity/verify endpoint, the same validated data is now used in this next stage to register the PID entities.

Figure 7 shows the /entity/register endpoint, where the user confirms the entityType (in this case, **audiovisual**) and submits the previously validated JSON file. Upon submission, the system executes the registration process and returns a job ID that can be used to track the status of this registration task.

POST /entity/register This method enables you to verify and register the PID entities and the metadata in the JSON file to be registered and returns a jobId to fetch the status of the registration process.

Register a JSON file containing PID entities to be registered, returns a jobId

Parameters Cancel

Name	Description
entityType * required string (query)	AUDIOVISUAL

Request body * required application/json

Examples:
audiovisual_valid.json

```
{
  "entities": [
    {
      "resourcePID": "10.4232/1.1690",
      "entityCode": "Video Clip",
      "entityLabel": "Main Video Clip",
      "entityType": "Audiovisual",
      "isFragment": false,
      "pidProposal": "21.111998/demo.test.1.1690.video",
      "landingPage": "https://search.gesis.org/variables/exploredata-ZA1690_video_clip",
      "title": "Video Clip",
      "creators": [
        {
          "institutionName": "GESIS"
        }
      ]
    },
    {
      "resourcePID": "10.4232/1.1690",
      "entityCode": "Video Clip"
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 7: Registering Validated Metadata via /entity/register

The Status Page is shown in Figure 8. After submitting a registration request via the /entity/register endpoint, each request is processed as a job and assigned a unique Job ID.

The table displayed lists all registration jobs submitted by the authenticated user (**qservice** in this case), along with:

- Job ID – the identifier of the registration job. Clicking it reveals detailed status info.
- Creation Date – when the job was initiated.
- Last Update – timestamp of the most recent job status change.
- Nr. of PidEntities – number of entities submitted in that job.
- Finished – how many entities were successfully registered.
- Pending/Running – jobs currently in progress.
- Failed – jobs that encountered errors.

After registration is initiated, users can track the progress of each job through the Status Page, where the job ID, timestamps, and success indicators are displayed. This page is essential for monitoring the outcome of each registration process and ensuring that all submitted PIDs have been successfully processed.

Jobs for User : **qservice**

#	Jobs ID	Creation Date	Last Update	Nr. of PidEntities	Finished	Pending/Running	Failed
1	3f8d851d-f043-4e51-a688-63f2583b650c	2025-08-01 14:48:05.419	2025-08-01 14:48:08.208	18	18	-	-
2	eece617d-8eda-4c08-98f8-53f6794f3c39	2025-08-01 11:15:12.578	2025-08-01 11:15:19.948	36	36	-	-
3	ee02768d-fb05-4e3a-9702-2409f8057c8a	2025-08-01 10:38:03.959	2025-08-01 10:38:46.961	143	143	-	-
4	72a251ce-7275-4c1b-8c9f-94dda8cfff21	2025-08-01 10:17:02.768	2025-08-01 10:17:24.391	89	89	-	-

Figure 8: Monitoring PID Registration Jobs

Figures 1 to 8 above illustrate the complete process of manually registering individual dataset elements using the KonsortSWD PID Registration Service. From metadata validation to job execution and status monitoring, each step was performed using test JSON files aligned with the updated schema for element-level registration. Building on this workflow, the following section presents the specific dataset elements registered during the Qualiservice test phase. These include various datatypes, such as text and video, for which PIDs were created. As Qualiservice test cases for specific data types like images were unavailable, we incorporated representative datasets from PANGAEA, since both share the same infrastructure.

3.2 Dataset elements registered for Qualiservice in the test phase

Dataset elements (e.g., text excerpts or audio/video segments) listed below were registered in the scope of this test phase. For each element, we registered the PID proposal, the landing page, and the metadata records stored as Kernel Information [14]. Qualiservice did not have available use cases for testing some data types, such as images. In these cases, we incorporated selected datasets from PANGAEA [15] to test PID registration, as PANGAEA and Qualiservice share the same underlying technical infrastructure and DOI registration service. This allowed us to test PID registration workflows and metadata mappings in a comparable environment. The following explanations illustrate how the metadata fields listed in Table 5 are applied in practice, focusing on two essential components for each registered element: the PID proposal and landing page, and the Kernel Information (PID Metadata Record) stored during the registration process.

3.2.1 The PID Proposal and the Landing Page

A unique PID proposal was created for each dataset element registered during the test phase. This proposal includes a custom identifier string using a test PID prefix (e.g., 21.T11199/demo.test.1.1680.video1). This syntax helps differentiate each element within the dataset. A standard on the PID syntax construction maintains consistency across the registration system. The landing page serves as the web-accessible entry point for each registered element. It provides essential information and context, as well as the parent dataset.

3.2.2 Metadata Records Stored as Kernel Information (PID Metadata Record)

Each registered PID is accompanied by a structured metadata record, encoded using Kernel Information, which is a standardized metadata profile designed to be minimal yet sufficient for machine-actionable services and interoperability. It includes all that is mapped from the parent dataset or explicitly provided for the element. By storing this information, the registration system enables discoverability, citation, and reuse of dataset elements. This approach supports long-term accessibility and traceability of PIDs.

3.3 Qualiservice PID for dataset elements: test phase implementation

The project team implemented a test phase in Qualiservice to demonstrate the feasibility of assigning PIDs to individual dataset elements in a qualitative context. The following subsection outlines the initial step in this process: mapping the existing metadata schema used by Qualiservice to the metadata requirements of the KonsortSWD PID Registration Service.

3.3.1 Mapping metadata

Table 5 illustrates the alignment between the metadata fields required by the PID Registration Service and the existing metadata available within the Qualiservice infrastructure, which is based on the PANGAEA system.

ID	ResourceType	PID Registration Service Metadata Schema	Mapped Qualiservice/PANGAEA Metadata Schema ¹⁶
1	Audiovisual, Image, Sound and Text	Study DOI	citation/URI (<i>dataset</i>)
2		Entity Name	Data ID or Case ID (<i>parameter</i>)
3		Entity Label	File name (<i>parameter</i>)
4		PID Proposal	N/A, the value is defined as a combination of the Test Prefix + Data ID and File Name
5		Landing Page	N/A, the value is defined as a combination of the Resolved URL by the Parent PID + Scroll-to-text parameter (see Section 3.2.2)
6		Resource Type	General data format ¹⁷ (<i>parameter</i>)
7		Title	Data ID-File name or File content (<i>parameter</i>)
8		Creators	citation/author (<i>dataset</i>)
9		Publisher	"PANGAEA" + citation/source (<i>dataset</i>)
10		Publication Date	citation/dateTime (<i>dataset</i>)
11		Availability	Access type (<i>dataset or parameter</i>)
12		Description	abstract (<i>dataset</i>) or File content, Keywords, or Annotation (<i>parameter</i>)

¹⁶ https://wiki.pangaea.de/wiki/PANGAEA_XML_schema and https://wiki.pangaea.de/wiki/Qualiservice_Parameters

¹⁷ <https://vocabularies.cessda.eu/urn/urn:ddi:int.ddi.cv:GeneralDataFormat:2.0.3?lang=en>

ID	ResourceType	PID Registration Service Metadata Schema	Mapped Qualiservice/PANGAEA Metadata Schema ¹⁸
Relation Container			
13	Audiovisual, Image, Sound and Text	RelatedItem	reference (<i>dataset</i>)
13.1		RelatedIdentifier	reference/URI
13.1.1		RelatedIdentifier_Type	N/A, the value is defined by the PID Syntax schema
13.1.2		Relation_Type	reference/@dataciteRelType
Dataset Element Container			
	Audiovisual	isFragment: true	-
		startOffset	Start offset (<i>parameter</i>)
		endOffset	End offset (<i>parameter</i>)
	Image	isFragment: true	-
		Shape	tbd
		Coordinates	tbd
	Sound	isFragment: true	-
		startOffset	Start offset (<i>parameter</i>)
		endOffset	End offset (<i>parameter</i>)
	Text	isFragment: true	-
		startCharOffset	tbd
		endCharOffset	tbd

Table 5: Metadata mapping between the PID registration Service and the Qualiservice dataset elements

The previous section outlined the metadata adjustments for registering persistent identifiers (PIDs) at the element level. However, the practical implementation faced some technical obstacles. The following section explores these hurdles, focusing on the issue of fragment visibility and the balance between granularity and usability in real-world data access scenarios.

3.3.2 Challenges

Fragment Accessibility and Visibility due to ambiguation

Qualiservice does not provide one landing page for each dataset element, but for the entire dataset, listing all the files. Only registered users can check the granular information, such as fragment, file, and case details, after logging in. At this point, selecting the table visualization or downloading it as a CSV is possible. A key challenge in this task is enabling landing pages to directly resolve to specific web content of elements, such as metadata or annotations. PIDs resolve to metadata elements, not to the actual files, since real data access requires contacting Qualiservice and signing usage agreements.

¹⁸ https://wiki.pangaea.de/wiki/PANGAEA_XML_schema and https://wiki.pangaea.de/wiki/Qualiservice_Parameters

Creating separate landing pages for each element is not practical. Especially for sensitive data, elements need to be interpreted in the context of the whole dataset. The main dataset landing page is, therefore, the proper access point.

Still, the PID must lead directly to the specific section of the landing page where the element's metadata is shown. In large tables, this helps researchers quickly find what they're looking for.

At the beginning of this project, a central technical question emerged: how can PID-linked URLs point to individual data elements on a landing page? Based on earlier exchanges, two possible strategies were proposed:

1. Static URI fragments using the #id attribute in HTML (e.g., https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.963249#GLOPRO_ANK_06), where an element's entityCode or entityLabel becomes a unique HTML ID.
2. Dynamic URL fragments using the #:-:text= syntax (as defined in the [Scroll-to-Text Fragment spec](#)¹⁹), which enables the browser to highlight matching text, even without explicitly defined HTML IDs.

While these methods enhance navigation, their implementation faces limitations:

- Static fragments (#id) require backend control or CMS access to inject ID attributes into HTML output.
- Dynamic text fragments (#:-:text=) depend heavily on browser support (works best in Google Chrome, being inconsistent or unsupported in Firefox and Safari), HTML structure, and visibility of the content (e.g., it must not be inside hidden or dynamically loaded elements like <td> within tables).
- Landing pages behind authentication barriers, such as Qualiservice's ORCID login, pose additional access limitations for fragment-level linking.
 - Example:
 - Qualiservice provides information on each dataset element by clicking "View dataset as HTML" in the *Download Data* Section. Users need to scroll down and may need to log in with their ORCID to see it, as depicted in Figures 9 and 10.

¹⁹ <https://wicg.github.io/scroll-to-text-fragment/#syntax>

Download Data (login required)

 Download dataset as tab-delimited text

 View dataset as HTML

Figure 9: Example of a login required to see the dataset elements' metadata

Figure 10 illustrates how metadata for individual text files is displayed on a landing page in a structured tabular format, supporting granular-level identification for PID registration. The PANGAEA landing page lists individual text fragments from qualitative interviews, each represented as a row in a downloadable table. The columns contain metadata such as file name, data format, event, language, participant background, etc. Although the page is accessible via a DOI, complete metadata visibility requires login authentication. This example also reflects how PANGAEA structures elements' metadata, despite potential browser compatibility issues with some HTML tags.

Data

 Download dataset as tab-delimited text — use the following character encoding:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
File name	Data format	Data label	Event	DC date	Event duration	Language	Gender	Prof. background	DC location	Activity start
BRIDGING_IT_01_StratExp5	Text	9	BRIDGING_01	2018	PT1H37M19S	deu	male	Theologie, Erziehungswissenschaft	Bavaria, Germany	1998
BRIDGING_IT_01_StratExp5	Text	9	BRIDGING_01	2018	PT1H37M19S	deu	female	Slavistik, Politikwissenschaft	Bavaria, Germany	2010
BRIDGING_IT_01_StratExp7	Text	12	BRIDGING_01	2018	PT59M24S	deu	male	Ausbildung/Pädagogik	Baden-Württemberg, Germany	1983
BRIDGING_IT_01_TaktExp8	Text	4	BRIDGING_01	2018	PT1H4M10S	deu	male	Betriebswirtschaftslehre, Promotion in Rechts- und Wirtschaftswissenschaften	Hamburg, Germany	2001
BRIDGING_IT_01_TaktExp12	Text	17	BRIDGING_01	2018	PT1H7M37S	deu	male	Physik/Mathematik	North Rhine-Westphalia, Germany	2014
BRIDGING_IT_02_FachExp0	Text	1	BRIDGING_02	2018	PT1H2M44S	deu	male	Kommunikationswissenschaften, Informationswissenschaften	Hamburg, Germany	2009
BRIDGING_IT_02_FachExp1	Text	6	BRIDGING_02	2018	PT1H8M46S	deu	male	Elektrotechnik	Bavaria, Germany	2008
BRIDGING_IT_02_FachExp2	Text	7	BRIDGING_02	2018	PT1H19M47S	deu	male	Mikroelektronik, Informatik	Bavaria, Germany	2011
BRIDGING_IT_02_FachExp3	Text	7	BRIDGING_02	2018	PT1H19M47S	deu	male	Elektro- und Informationstechnik	Bavaria, Germany	2010
BRIDGING_IT_02_FachExp3	Text	14	BRIDGING_02	2018	PT1H8M26S	deu	female	Pädagogik	North Rhine-Westphalia, Germany	2005
BRIDGING_IT_02_FachExp4	Text	15	BRIDGING_02	2018	PT53M39S	deu	male	Mathematik	North Rhine-Westphalia, Germany	2006
BRIDGING_IT_02_FachExp5	Text	10	BRIDGING_02	2018	PT1H6M25S	deu	male	Chemie	Bavaria, Germany	2012
BRIDGING_IT_02_FachExp5	Text	10	BRIDGING_02	2018	PT1H6M25S	deu	male	Chemie, Chemie und Biologie	Bavaria, Germany	2000
BRIDGING_IT_03_StratExp11	Text	13	BRIDGING_03	2019	PT1H9M54S	deu	male		Saxony-Anhalt, Germany	
BRIDGING_IT_03_TaktExp18	Text	10	BRIDGING_03	2019	PT1H16M55S	deu	male	Medieninformatik, E-Learning, Mathematik	Saxony, Germany	1998

Figure 10: Example of a text file's landing page DOI 10.1594/PANGAEA.930449

Available at <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.930449?format=html#download> (login required)

- Some web implementations (e.g., PANGAEA's use of id for <th>) successfully support these features, while others (like <td>) are not fully compliant across browsers or not implemented consistently.

The project analyzes standards to guide the technical implementation of scroll-to-text or scroll-to-segment features to support these technical goals. To highlight specific textual content (such as segment names, codes, etc.), our current strategy with `#:-:text=` is more appropriate because it is more flexible and does not depend on id attributes in the page's

HTML. However, it is more uncontrollable at the browser-client side. We used this feature to ensure that Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) can link directly to specific parts of a digital resource (such as text excerpts or video segments) or its metadata. We considered the following international standards:

- RFC3986 for URI syntax– Defines the general syntax for URIs, including using fragment identifiers (#) to navigate within HTML documents. <https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc3986>
- W3C Annotation Model for fragment selectors– Provides a model and syntax for identifying and annotating specific parts of a resource using fragment selectors. It supports a variety of MIME types, including HTML and XML. <https://www.w3.org/TR/annotation-model/#fragment-selector>
- W3C Media Fragments URI 1.0 – Specifies a standardized way to reference spatial and temporal segments of media resources, such as audio, video, and images, using fragments like #t=10,20 or #xywh=160,120,320,240. <https://www.w3.org/TR/media-frags/>

These serve as technical guidance for both #id anchoring and #-:text= highlighting approaches, crucial for enhancing navigability and citation resolution.

Standard	Purpose	Link
RFC 3986	Defines general URI syntax, including #fragment notation	https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc3986
W3C Annotation Model	Supports text fragment annotation across various MIME types	https://www.w3.org/TR/annotation-model/#fragment-selector
W3C Media Fragments 1.0	Enables time and spatial targeting in audiovisual and image content	https://www.w3.org/TR/media-frags/

Table 6: Technical guidance for #id anchoring and #-:text=

Since only one landing page per dataset is available, the Landing page information was the same for all registered elements.

The lack of a dedicated landing page for each dataset element is not a limitation for persistent identification. According to RFC 3986, the fragment can identify a secondary resource within a primary one.

This approach is widely used in semantic web practices and ontologies, where individual terms are identified through fragments on a shared page, like:

- <https://d-nb.info/standards/elementset/gnd#Family> (HTML id)
- <https://www.w3.org/ns/org#memberOf> (RDF term)

Similarly, dataset elements in Qualiservice can be referenced through element identifiers pointing to specific metadata sections within a single landing page. The PID remains a valid and unique reference even if the browser cannot visually highlight the element.

Additionally, when using content negotiation and structured metadata formats (e.g., tabular formats), services can use RFC 7111 to refer to specific rows in a CSV. Example:

```
<link rel="item" href="https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.970274?format=textfile" type="text/tab-separated-values">
```

This enables machine-actionable access to individual dataset elements without requiring a separate page per item.

As a preliminary solution, we adopted the feature Scroll-to-text fragments to highlight a fragment in the table. See 3.2.2 Challenges.

3.3.3 Guidance

The Project's team provided detailed guidance in this regard. Some implementable suggestions to improve web infrastructure (e.g., scroll features for partners like PANGAEA) are detailed in Table 6.

Solution	Description	Outcome
Add ID to HTML elements	Add <code><td id="SegmentName">...</td></code>	Enables scrolling via URL <code>#SegmentName</code>
Use JavaScript (e.g., Mark.js)	Automatically highlights matching text inside tags like <code><td></code> , <code><pre></code>	Allows reliable highlighting independent of HTML structure
Use <code></code> as anchors	Insert invisible anchors near relevant content	Enables smooth scrolling via fragment identifiers

Table 7: Improve scroll features suggestions.

However, it is possible to automate the creation of ID attributes in HTML for each table element. The feasibility of this approach depends on how the HTML is generated.

If the HTML is generated automatically (e.g., via script or CMS), you can:

- Iterate through each cell in the table with a script (in Python, JavaScript, or another language).
- Add an id attribute to each `<td>` or `<tr>` using a unique identifier (such as `entityCode`, `entityLabel`, or another key).
- Regenerate the HTML with these new IDs.

If you have access to a static HTML (.html file), helpful tools include:

- **BeautifulSoup (Python)** – to locate each cell and dynamically insert ID attributes.

- **CMS plugins** – if using WordPress, Drupal, etc., plugins exist to automate ID insertion.

In all cases, we need to define which elements should be registered. The strategic decision (what to register and make citable) is likely more critical than the technical approach. Still, these options can be included in the report if many elements are relevant for PID registration and lack unique landing pages. These steps would help mitigate the scroll-to-text limitations.

We acknowledge that full implementation may exceed the test phase scope, but these challenges were documented for future consideration.

3.3.4 Achievements

Achievements can be measured by fulfilling the objectives for this project during the implementation phase. Adjustments and recommendations on implementing PIDs at a lower granularity level, considering a strategic approach, and evaluating the trade-off between effort and benefits are also valuable contributions from this short project. Also, other more subjective aspects were improved, such as knowledge exchange and strengthened collaboration between the leading and use case partner institutions. Table 6 refers to the objectives and where they are presented in this report.

Short Project Objectives	Section/resource
Mapping the data model of the Qualiservice system to match the PID registration metadata schema for conceptualizing a test phase.	Section 3.2.1 and Table 5
Create JSON files with the required metadata for manual PID registration	Supplementary data
Test PIDs registered through the manual process using JSON files	Table 4 and Section 6
Propose infrastructure adjustments for sustainable integration.	Sections 3 and 4

Table 8: Achieved objectives presented in this report

Section 4 addresses the necessary adjustments to the Qualiservice metadata portal to support PID registration at a finer level of granularity. These adjustments include extended landing page capabilities, improved metadata export support, and citation integration.

4. Consolidated Recommendations and Metadata Adjustments for PID Registration in Qualiservice

This section presents the following recommendations to summarize the implementation approach. These adjustments are recommendations and metadata adherence to support FAIR-compliant persistent identification of dataset elements. These are intended as practical guidance for research data centers dealing with qualitative data that aim to implement persistent identifiers below the dataset level, since the pilot implementation of the PID Registration Service with Qualiservice provided key insights for future implementation.

4.1 Fragment-Level Landing Pages

Each fragment (e.g., video clip, interview excerpt, transcript excerpt) must be assigned a persistent and resolvable URL redirecting to a landing page with element-specific metadata. This follows the W3C standards for fragment identifiers and is a prerequisite for PID resolution.

Recommendation:

Implement fragment-specific URLs embedded in landing pages that contain human and machine-readable metadata. Ensure that such pages allow citation, navigation, and metadata harvesting. Avoid HTML table rows as final targets for PID resolution, mainly when access is restricted. See section 3.2.3. For further guidance on implementing the suggested URL-fragment approach for landing pages providing metadata about dataset elements.

4.2 Extend Metadata Schema for Element-Level Description

Section 3 and Table 1 state that the PID registration metadata schema must be extended to support entity-specific attributes. Qualiservice's internal schema should be reviewed, and, where necessary, parameters should be added to allow for fragment-level precision.

Recommendation:

- **Entity Type:** Drawn from controlled vocabularies such as DataCite or DDI.
- **Fragment Location:** Use markers like time codes (AV files), character offsets (text), or coordinates (images).
- **Entity Relationships:** Model relationships between elements (e.g., text excerpts belong to text files, video segments belong to audiovisual files).

4.3 Standardize Controlled Vocabulary Usage

Metadata fields such as the field `ResourceType` and `entityType` should use controlled vocabularies such as:

- Text File / Transcript Excerpt
- Audio Segment / Video Segment
- Image Area

Currently, the DDI controlled vocabulary “General Data Format” <https://vocabularies.cessda.eu/urn/urn:ddi:int.ddi.cv:GeneralDataFormat:2.0.3> and the controlled list for “DataCite resourceTypeGeneral” <https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.6/appendices/appendix-1/resourceTypeGeneral/> have been used to identify the type of elements that compose the dataset.

Recommendation

Use a mapping strategy that combines the above vocabularies with internal PID Registration Service fields and flags such as `isFragment`. If `ResourceType` should also be specified for parts of a file, mapping could help by combining the available information about the general data format.²⁰ and the `isFragment` flag.

4.4 Enable Export and Citation Integration

Researchers should be directed in familiar workflows to use assigned PIDs actively. Integrating PIDs into citation exports, such as RIS, BibTeX, Zotero, or Mendeley will consistently support referencing dataset elements or files. JSON metadata files must be exportable at the element level to foster citation and reuse. We suggest providing element-specific metadata in standard citation formats within reference management tools (i.e., BibTeX, RIS, and other compatible formats).

Recommendation:

- Extend HTML metadata views to include element-specific JSON exports.
- Update citation export tools to reflect the PID of elements when available.

²⁰ https://wiki.pangaea.de/wiki/Qualiservice_Parameters#Table

4.5 Promote Knowledge Graph Compatibility and Linked Data Integration

The metadata schema should incorporate fields compatible with RDF vocabularies to enable inclusion in semantic knowledge graphs and Linked Data environments. PIDs can be linked semantically by extended fields such as `RelatedItem`, `RelationType`, and `RelatedIdentifier`, which are essential for knowledge graph compatibility.

Recommendation:

- Extend metadata fields and document dataset elements' relations using PIDs as metadata values
- Use extended metadata fields such as `RelatedItem`, `Relation_Type`, and `RelatedIdentifier` to enable graph-based exploration and semantic search.
- Adopt typed links as described in the FAIR Signposting Profile [16], including `describedby`, `license`, `item`, and `collection`, enabling HTTP-based link navigation.

4.6 Balance metadata granularity with practical feasibility

While fine-grained PID assignment enhances accurate citation and traceability, registering all elements is not always feasible. A use case analysis approach is suggested. For instance, full interviews might be registered instead of each quote, unless quotes are independently reused.

Recommendation:

- Prioritize element-level PIDs for cases with high reuse, citation, or replication potential.
- Use iterative testing (e.g., start with a few segments) to refine use cases before scaling. The Qualiservice short project followed this approach. We started by manually mapping and registering the metadata schema using JSON files. Then, we moved to monitoring via jobsID dashboards in the PID registration Service. This iterative cycle allowed for the refinement of workflows before planning automation and larger-scale ingestion.

Section 5 compiles supporting figures and tables, while Section 6 (Appendix) provides sample metadata and test PIDs for all major entity types: audiovisual, image, sound, and text, including both complete resources and their respective segments/fragments.

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6 Appendix

6.1 Appendix 1: Test PIDs for **Audiovisual** entity type

a) Audiovisual Full

#	Pid Entities	Status	Validati-on Status	Validati-on Errors	Final PID	PID Record Metadata	Registration Result
3	<u>Audiovisua</u> <u>l-2</u>	FINISHED	valid	-	<u>21.T11998/qservice.test-</u> <u>GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOP</u> <u>RO_VID_ANK_Can_02</u>	<u>21.T11998/qservice.test-</u> <u>GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOP</u> <u>RO_VID_ANK_Can_02</u>	created:201
2	<u>Audiovisua</u> <u>l-1</u>	FINISHED	valid	-	<u>21.T11998/qservice.test-</u> <u>GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOP</u> <u>RO_RAW_ANK_Can_02</u>	<u>21.T11998/qservice.test-</u> <u>GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOP</u> <u>RO_RAW_ANK_Can_02</u>	created:201
1	<u>Audiovisua</u> <u>l-0</u>	FINISHED	valid	-	<u>21.T11998/qservice.test-</u> <u>GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOP</u> <u>RO_RAW_ANK_Can_01</u>	<u>21.T11998/qservice.test-</u> <u>GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOP</u> <u>RO_RAW_ANK_Can_01</u>	created:201

#	PidEntities	Status	Validation Status	Validation Errors	Final PID	PID Record Metadata	Registration Result
11	Audiovisual-10	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_03_GLOPRO_RAW_ANK_Ertekin_01	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_03_GLOPRO_RAW_ANK_Ertekin_01	created:201
10	Audiovisual-9	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_02_GLOPRO_TRS-ELAN_ANK_Demir	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_02_GLOPRO_TRS-ELAN_ANK_Demir	created:201
9	Audiovisual-8	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_02_GLOPRO_VID-ELAN_ANK_Demir	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_02_GLOPRO_VID-ELAN_ANK_Demir	created:201
8	Audiovisual-7	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_02_GLOPRO_VID_ANK_Demir_02	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_02_GLOPRO_VID_ANK_Demir_02	created:201
7	Audiovisual-6	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_02_GLOPRO_RAW_ANK_Demir_02	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_02_GLOPRO_RAW_ANK_Demir_02	created:201

6	Audiovisual-5	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_02_GLOPRO_RAW_ANK_Demir_01	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_02_GLOPRO_RAW_ANK_Demir_01	created:201
5	Audiovisual-4	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOPRO_TRS-ELAN_ANK_Can	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOPRO_TRS-ELAN_ANK_Can	created:201
4	Audiovisual-3	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOPRO_VID-ELAN_ANK_Can	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOPRO_VID-ELAN_ANK_Can	created:201
3	Audiovisual-2	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOPRO_VID_ANK_Can_02	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOPRO_VID_ANK_Can_02	created:201
2	Audiovisual-1	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOPRO_RAW_ANK_Can_02	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOPRO_RAW_ANK_Can_02	created:201

1	<u>Audiovisu</u> <u>al-0</u>	FINISH ED	valid	-	<u>21.T11998/qservice.test-</u> <u>GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOPRO_RAW_ANK</u> <u>_Can_01</u>	<u>21.T11998/qservice.test-</u> <u>GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOPRO_RAW_ANK</u> <u>_Can_01</u>	created:2 01
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#	PidEntites	Status	Validati on Status	Validati on Errors	Final PID	PID Record Metadata	Registrat ion Result
1 1	<u>Audiovisu</u> <u>al-10</u>	FINISH ED	valid	-	<u>21.T11998/qservice.test-</u> <u>GLOPRO_ANK_03_GLOPRO_RAW_ANK</u> <u>_Ertekin_01</u>	<u>21.T11998/qservice.test-</u> <u>GLOPRO_ANK_03_GLOPRO_RAW_ANK</u> <u>_Ertekin_01</u>	created:2 01
1 0	<u>Audiovisu</u> <u>al-9</u>	FINISH ED	valid	-	<u>21.T11998/qservice.test-</u> <u>GLOPRO_ANK_02_GLOPRO_TRS-</u> <u>ELAN_ANK_Demir</u>	<u>21.T11998/qservice.test-</u> <u>GLOPRO_ANK_02_GLOPRO_TRS-</u> <u>ELAN_ANK_Demir</u>	created:2 01
9	<u>Audiovisu</u> <u>al-8</u>	FINISH ED	valid	-	<u>21.T11998/qservice.test-</u> <u>GLOPRO_ANK_02_GLOPRO_VID-</u> <u>ELAN_ANK_Demir</u>	<u>21.T11998/qservice.test-</u> <u>GLOPRO_ANK_02_GLOPRO_VID-</u> <u>ELAN_ANK_Demir</u>	created:2 01

8	Audiovisual-7	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_02_GLOPRO_VID_ANK_Demir_02	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_02_GLOPRO_VID_ANK_Demir_02	created:201
7	Audiovisual-6	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_02_GLOPRO_RAW_ANK_Demir_02	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_02_GLOPRO_RAW_ANK_Demir_02	created:201
6	Audiovisual-5	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_02_GLOPRO_RAW_ANK_Demir_01	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_02_GLOPRO_RAW_ANK_Demir_01	created:201
5	Audiovisual-4	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOPRO_TRS-ELAN_ANK_Can	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOPRO_TRS-ELAN_ANK_Can	created:201
4	Audiovisual-3	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOPRO_VID-ELAN_ANK_Can	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOPRO_VID-ELAN_ANK_Can	created:201

3	Audiovisual-2	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOPRO_VID_ANK_Can_02	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOPRO_VID_ANK_Can_02	created:201
2	Audiovisual-1	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOPRO_RAW_ANK_Can_02	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOPRO_RAW_ANK_Can_02	created:201
1	Audiovisual-0	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOPRO_RAW_ANK_Can_01	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_01_GLOPRO_RAW_ANK_Can_01	created:201

b) Audiovisual Fragments

#	PidEntities	Status	Validation Status	Validation Errors	Final PID	PID Record Metadata	Registration Result
1	Audiovisual-5	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-BC_01_03-AA0876_01-converted.mp4	21.T11998/qservice.test-BC_01_03-AA0876_01-converted.mp4	created:201
2	Audiovisual-1	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-BC_01_02-AA0875_01-converted.mp4	21.T11998/qservice.test-BC_01_02-AA0875_01-converted.mp4	created:201

3	Audiovisual-0	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-BC_01_01-AA0874_01-converted.mp4	21.T11998/qservice.test-BC_01_01-AA0874_01-converted.mp4	created:201
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Main table: See Table 4: Dataset elements registered in the scope of this short project

6.2 Appendix 2: Test PIDs for **Image** entity type

a) Image Full

#	PidEntities	Status	Validation Status	Validation Errors	Final PID	PID Record Metadata	Registration Result
1	Image-2	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-Atka11_S70_35_617_W07_48_426-DSC_4025	21.T11998/qservice.test-Atka11_S70_35_617_W07_48_426-DSC_4025	updated:204
2	Image-1	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-Atka11_S70_35_617_W07_48_426-DSC_4024	21.T11998/qservice.test-Atka11_S70_35_617_W07_48_426-DSC_4024	updated:204
3	Image-0	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-Atka11_S70_35_617_W07_48_426-DSC_4023	21.T11998/qservice.test-Atka11_S70_35_617_W07_48_426-DSC_4023	updated:204

b) Image Fragments

#	PidEntities	Status	Validation Status	Validation Errors	Final PID	PID Record Metadata	Registration Result
1	Image-2	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-Atka11_S70_35_617_W07_48_426-DSC_4037	21.T11998/qservice.test-Atka11_S70_35_617_W07_48_426-DSC_4037	updated:204
2	Image-1	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-Atka11_S70_35_617_W07_48_426-DSC_4036	21.T11998/qservice.test-Atka11_S70_35_617_W07_48_426-DSC_4036	updated:204
3	Image-0	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-Atka11_S70_35_617_W07_48_426-DSC_4035	21.T11998/qservice.test-Atka11_S70_35_617_W07_48_426-DSC_4035	updated:204

Main table: See Table 4: Dataset elements registered in the scope of this short project

6.3 Appendix 3: Test PIDs for **Sound** entity type

a) Sound Full

#	Pid Entities	Status	Validation Status	Validation Errors	Final PID	PID Record Metadata	Registration Result
9	Sound-2	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_03GLOPRO_AUD_A_UD_ANK_Ertekin	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_03GLOPRO_AUD_A_NK_Ertekin	updated:204
10	Sound-1	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_02GLOPRO_AUD_ANK_Demir	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_02GLOPRO_AUD_A_NK_Demir	updated:204
11	Sound-0	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_01GLOPRO_AUD_ANK_Can	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_01GLOPRO_AUD_A_NK_Can	updated:204

#	Pid Entities	Status	Validation Status	Validation Errors	Final PID	PID Record Metadata	Registration Result
1	Sound-10	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_AUD_ANK_11GLOPRO_AUD_ANK_Nalci	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_AUD_ANK_11GLOPRO_AUD_ANK_Nalci	updated:204
2	Sound-9	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_AUD_ANK_10GLOPRO_AUD_ANK_Mumcu	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_AUD_ANK_10GLOPRO_AUD_ANK_Mumcu	updated:204

3	Sound-8	FINISH ED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO ANK 09GLOPRO AUD ANK _Layik	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO ANK 09GLOPRO AUD ANK _Layik	updated:2 04
4	Sound-7	FINISH ED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO ANK 08GLOPRO AUD ANK _Ko	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO ANK 08GLOPRO AUD ANK _Ko	updated:2 04
5	Sound-6	FINISH ED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO ANK 07GLOPRO AUD ANK _Isik	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO ANK 07GLOPRO AUD ANK _Isik	updated:2 04
6	Sound-5	FINISH ED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO ANK 06GLOPRO AUD ANK _Hakan	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO ANK 06GLOPRO AUD ANK _Hakan	updated:2 04
7	Sound-4	FINISH ED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO ANK 05GLOPRO AUD ANK _Gu	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO ANK 05GLOPRO AUD ANK _Gu	updated:2 04
8	Sound-3	FINISH ED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO ANK 04GLOPRO AUD ANK _Felek	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO ANK 04GLOPRO AUD ANK _Felek	updated:2 04
9	Sound-2	FINISH ED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO ANK 03GLOPRO AUD ANK _Ertekin	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO ANK 03GLOPRO AUD ANK _Ertekin	updated:2 04
10	Sound-1	FINISH ED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO ANK 02GLOPRO AUD ANK _Demir	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO ANK 02GLOPRO AUD ANK _Demir	updated:2 04
11	Sound-0	FINISH ED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO ANK 01GLOPRO AUD ANK _Can	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO ANK 01GLOPRO AUD ANK _Can	updated:2 04

b) Sound Fragments

#	Pid Entities	Status	Validation Status	Validation Errors	Final PID	PID Record Metadata	Registration Result
1	Audiovisual-11	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-BC_01_20-AA0893_01-converted.mp4	21.T11998/qservice.test-BC_01_20-AA0893_01-converted.mp4	created:201
2	Audiovisual-10	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-BC_01_05-AA0878_01-converted.mp4	21.T11998/qservice.test-BC_01_05-AA0878_01-converted.mp4	created:201
3	Audiovisual-7	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-BC_01_04-AA0877_01-converted.mp4	21.T11998/qservice.test-BC_01_04-AA0877_01-converted.mp4	created:201

Main table. See Table 4: Dataset elements registered in the scope of this short project

6.4 Appendix 4: Test PIDs for **Text** entity type

a) Text Full

#	Pid Entities	Status	Validation Status	Validation Errors	Final PID	PID Record Metadata	Registration Result
1	Text-2	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_02GLOPRO_TRS_AN S_ANK_Demir	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_02GLOPRO_TRS_AN K_Demir	updated:204
2	Text-1	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_01GLOPRO_TRS-eng ANK_Can	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_01GLOPRO_TRS-eng ANK_Can	updated:204
3	Text-0	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_01GLOPRO_TRS ANK_Can	21.T11998/qservice.test-GLOPRO_ANK_01GLOPRO_TRS_AN K_Can	updated:204

b) Text Fragments

#	PidEntities	Status	Validation Status	Validation Errors	Final PID	PID Record Metadata	Registration Result
1	Text-2	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-BRIDGING_01_TEXT3	21.T11998/qservice.test-BRIDGING_01_TEXT3	updated:204
2	Text-1	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-BRIDGING_01_TEXT2	21.T11998/qservice.test-BRIDGING_01_TEXT2	updated:204
3	Text-0	FINISHED	valid	-	21.T11998/qservice.test-BRIDGING_01_TEXT1	21.T11998/qservice.test-BRIDGING_01_TEXT1	updated:204

Main table. See Table 4: Dataset elements registered in the scope of this short project

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